

Title of the Manuscript:

Resilience in the Circular Economy: Perspectives for Better Alignment

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1 Resilience in the Circular Economy: 2 Perspectives for Better Alignment

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5 *Perspective article for Resources, Conservation & Recycling – Special Issue ‘From Metrics*
6 *to Decisions’*

7 This perspective article addresses the role of systemic resilience in circular economy (CE)
8 debates. It underlines resilience as an important feature and proposes ways of how CE metrics
9 and decision-making could be better aligned.

10 **Why resilience needs more attention**

11 The CE has primarily been promoted as a strategy to advance environmental goals.
12 Nowadays, it is hoped to strengthen resource sovereignty and enhance systemic resilience —
13 qualities that gain relevance as geopolitical tensions, protectionism and economic
14 uncertainties intensify. By extending product lifetimes, improving resource efficiency, and
15 recovering secondary materials, CE is expected to reduce dependence on primary resource
16 imports, buffer volatile global supply chains, and increase competitiveness of national
17 industries. However, the concept of resilience enters CE debates just slowly (Kennedy &
18 Linnenluecke, 2022; De Angelis, 2022). We claim it needs more rigour, how it could be
19 embedded in metrics and frameworks used to guide decision-making. Existing approaches
20 capture circularity rates and material flows but provide limited insight into system behaviour
21 under stress, the distribution of risks, or the capacity of adaptive response. This gap is
22 particularly visible in the context of critical raw materials (CRM), whose supply chains combine
23 high strategic importance with structural vulnerabilities. Despite their relevance, recovery and
24 recycling rates remain low for key materials such as lithium and rare earth elements, even as
25 demand rises rapidly due to the energy transition. This highlights a broader limitation of CE
26 strategies: improving material efficiency does not easily translate into more resilient systems.

27 Our article offers two complementary perspectives: the role of CE in strengthening resource
28 sovereignty to foster resilience under shifting geopolitical conditions, and in designing resilient
29 circular systems.

30

31 **Connecting the dots: a resilient circular economy**

32 Resilience refers to the ability of a system to absorb shocks, adapt to change, and transform
33 where necessary—all without giving up its core identity and functions. This “adaptive capacity”
34 depends on several key features: diversity and redundancy provide alternative options when
35 parts of the system fail; modularity helps contain disruptions and avoid system-wide
36 breakdowns; and polycentric governance allows for flexible and decentralised responses.
37 Reflexivity plays a central role in enabling such capacity to transform, as it allows actors to
38 critically reassess underlying assumptions and adapt governance frameworks accordingly.

39 These key features, however, are not automatically strengthened by CE strategies. A CE
40 emphasis on closing and optimising resource loops can actually reduce diversity, eliminate
41 redundancy, and increase system tightness. While this improves efficiency, it may also
42 increase vulnerability to disruptions. This trade-off becomes particularly pronounced in CRM
43 supply chains where primary production is geographically concentrated and substitution
44 options are limited. CE strategies could, in principle, diversify supply through secondary
45 recovery. But to tap in this potential, circular systems need to be designed with resilience in
46 mind: multiple recovery pathways, distributed process capacity, and buffering (incl. pricing)
47 mechanisms to mitigate disruptions. Thus, circularity is not inherently resilience-enhancing but
48 contingent on system design. This may explain why raw material criticality and supply risk
49 management rarely integrate circular economy dynamics (Geng, Sarkis, Bleischwitz 2023;
50 Otterbach & Fröhling, 2025).

51 This conceptual blind spot also extends to distributional and spatial concerns: Current CE
52 approaches largely ignore who bears the costs and risks of circular strategies, and who
53 benefits. Extraction regions are often exposed to environmental and economic pressures, yet
54 have limited influence over the organisation of international value chains. Strategies that
55 improve resource security for one region while shifting pressures elsewhere do not build
56 resilience but rather redistribute vulnerability and burdens. With progress on SDG 12 stalling
57 and inequalities in global resource use rising, these asymmetries are deepening rather than
58 closing. A resilience perspective for CE must therefore address spatial issues explicitly and
59 incorporate justice and inclusivity as core conditions alongside with diversity, adaptive
60 capacity, and polycentric governance.

61 **Why a resilient CE requires cybernetic thinking**

62 A perspective to operationalise resilience in CE can be drawn from cybernetics (see figure).
63 Cybernetics provides a framework for processing information, feedback loops, and decision

64 rules to enable systems to work under disruptions and uncertainty. Highly complex CE
65 systems can be modelled as closed-loop configurations of action, sensing, feedback and
66 decision. Cybernetics has been applied in areas such as industrial management and
67 macroeconomic policy, e.g. the European Central Bank already treats the economy as a
68 dynamic system controlled through feedback under uncertainty. However, this perspective has
69 rarely been applied to the design of CE metrics or digital infrastructures supporting CE.
70 Research should advance how a digitally supported CE can actually function as a closed-loop
71 feedback system that tracks material flows with detecting vulnerabilities and identifying how
72 risks and costs are distributed when disruptions occur or strategies fail. Adopting a cybernetic
73 perspective thus shifts the focus from measuring system states to designing closed-loop
74 control strategies for dynamic feedback systems that support adaptive decision-making - with
75 an understanding of resilience not as bouncing back but rather bouncing forward in the context
76 of transformation strategies (Bharwani et al. 2026).

77

78 **Implications for metric design easing decision-making**

79 Robust decision-making requires CE metrics that extend beyond static material flow indicators
80 to measure how the system performs under stress. Becoming spatially more explicit is a task
81 for which additional analysis based on available data seems feasible. The first additional layer
82 should then capture *adaptive and transformative capacity*, i.e. the ability of a system to
83 respond to disturbances and to change in a forward-looking manner. For CRM, supply source

84 diversity, material substitutability, and response latency to disruptions could be assessed.
85 Tools such as GVC-exposure metrics (Baldwin & Freeman, 2022) are useful starting points.

86 A second future layer would measure *reflexive capacity*: whether systems can recognise and
87 address their own limitations. This includes the ability to detect burden shifting and to include
88 affected stakeholders in governance. Cybernetics offers useful concepts here—polycentricity
89 distributes agency across decision-making nodes, and diversity implies that excluding
90 perspectives reduces the system’s adaptive capacity. However, reflexive capacity cannot be
91 reduced to a set of measurable variables, such as the share of vulnerable communities
92 represented in governing bodies. It also requires an explicit articulation of inherent veto voices
93 of incumbents, transition capability, causal logics, and impact pathways, through which circular
94 interventions shape system and actors behaviour, including how they may reduce, redistribute
95 or inadvertently amplify vulnerabilities. Furthermore, normative questions about fairness
96 require ethical frameworks that cybernetics does not generate internally.

97 Digital tools can support such a multi-layered framework. Digital Product Passports, mandated
98 under the EU Battery Regulation and Critical Raw Materials Act, can link material flows to real-
99 time data on composition, origin and end-of-life pathways, converting the static snapshots of
100 material flow analysis into decision-relevant resilience signals (Zhang & Seuring, 2024).
101 Digitally enabled anthropogenic stock registries and AI-assisted material platforms can further
102 map secondary reserves that existing metrics leave unmapped, helping address persistent
103 recovery gaps for materials such as lithium. Physical trade data with metrics on components
104 and pre-products should be aligned, and analysis on port cities included.

105 Although digitalisation can and should inspire more research on resilient capacities of CE
106 systems rather than maintaining a status quo, it may also introduce new inequalities: countries
107 bearing the extraction burden are precisely those least equipped to participate in or benefit
108 from digital CE platforms, with fewer than 27% of populations in least developed countries
109 currently online. Whether digital tools narrow or deepen these asymmetries depends, again,
110 on governance. Open data standards, interoperability requirements, and technology transfer
111 must therefore be preconditions, not aspirational add-ons, of any international CE alliance. An
112 international database with forecasts on secondary material availability could help develop fair
113 trade and other standards.

114 **Outlook**

115 CE and resilience are not natural twins, despite some similarities. CE should become more
116 explicit on how it contributes to resilience for supply chains and societies. Becoming more

117 resilient requires moving beyond loop-closure metrics and including the full range of available
118 data toward a multi-layered assessment framework that captures adaptive capacity and
119 reflexive governance alongside material circularity. CRM illustrate the urgency of this shift.
120 Cybernetics offers useful approaches to operationalise an alignment of metrics with decision-
121 making. In a perspective, a flagship CE alliance between the middle powers of Europe,
122 Australia, Canada, Japan, South Korea, and main supplier countries with refining capacities
123 could be established with an international database, transdisciplinary peer learning and
124 knowledge cooperation for secondary material markets.

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